

A study of the influence of AI algorithms on human behavior and changes in the basic values of Russian society

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Аннотация. Проблематика исследования влияния алгоритмов искусственного интеллекта (ИИ) на сознание отдельного индивида и общества в целом в настоящее время представляется очень актуальной. С учетом современной геополитической ситуации принципиально важно минимизировать риски негативного воздействия алгоритмов ИИ на цивилизационные ценности российского общества. Кроме чисто экономических аспектов в исследовании представлены психологические и культурно-философские оценки. Установлено, что серьезную опасность для дальнейшей эволюции всего человечества представляет стремление разработчиков алгоритмов ИИ к унификации информации. Сделан вывод о необходимости снижения негативного воздействия алгоритмов ИИ на цивилизационные ценности российского общества и целесообразности продолжения исследований манипулятивного воздействия алгоритмов ИИ на общественное сознание по некоторым значимым факторам.

Abstract. The problem of studying the influence of artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms on the consciousness of an individual and society as a whole currently seems to be very relevant. Given the current geopolitical situation, it is fundamentally important to minimize the risks of the negative impact of AI algorithms on the civilizational values of Russian society. In addition to purely economic aspects, the study presents psychological and cultural-philosophical assessments. It has been established that the desire of AI algorithm developers to unify information poses a serious danger to the further evolution of all mankind. A conclusion has been made about the need to reduce the negative impact of AI algorithms on the civilizational values of Russian society and the advisability of continuing research into the manipulative impact of AI algorithms on public consciousness for some significant factors.

Ключевые слова: искусственный интеллект, алгоритмы, влияние, цивилизационные ценности, российское общество, факторы.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, algorithms, influence, civilizational values, Russian society, factors.

Introduction

The issues of safe use of AI algorithms were first discussed in a serious and broad manner at the Bletchley Park Summit in the UK in 2023 [1]. Following the summit, a declaration was published calling for international cooperation to address the challenges and risks associated with the development of AI. All participants supported the proposal to develop, implement and use AI algorithms in a safe, human-centered and trustworthy manner.

The second AI Safety Summit was held in Seoul on May 21-22, 2024. Its participants adopted and signed the Seoul Ministerial Statement on Advancing AI Safety, Innovation and Inclusion. For the first time, participating countries agreed on the need to develop common risk thresholds for the advanced development and deployment of AI. 16 companies

leading the development of AI algorithms made a commitment to the safe development of this technology. It was proposed for companies to set risk thresholds beyond which they will not release their models. Among them were leaders from the USA: Google, Meta, Microsoft and OpenAI. The companies that committed to ensuring security included: Zhipu.ai, supported by Chinese companies Alibaba, Tencent, Meituan and Xiaomi, the UAE Institute of Technological Innovation, Amazon, IBM and Samsung Electronics. They pledged to avoid models in which risks cannot be sufficiently mitigated, for example, in the case of cyberattacks [2].

The problems of the security of AI algorithms also cause controversial debates in society. Here, the key issue is not the speed of AI development, and not the risk thresholds, but the technological capabilities

of using AI algorithms for targeted management of public consciousness. In this regard, it seems appropriate to summarize the results of a number of modern studies on current issues in order to develop further approaches and specify the directions of analysis.

Main part

As a result of the research conducted by the authors, the results of scientific research by well-known Russian and foreign authors on the issues of this article were systematized in two directions.

1. The influence of AI algorithms on human behavior

The dynamics of socio-economic processes in the information society confirms the existence of trends that pose a danger to the future development of all mankind. They consist in the possibility of manipulating the consciousness of both an individual and society as a whole. This is carried out by influencing the cognitive abilities of a person using AI algorithms.

As is known, all content on the English-language Internet is generated using a set of keywords. Therefore, content developers can adapt their prejudices and fictions to their perception in the public consciousness without any verification. As a result, any disinformation spreads rapidly and, due to the targeted use of language models, influences public consciousness. As a result, individuals lose the ability to distinguish lies from truth and allow their consciousness to be easily manipulated.

Until now, these issues have not been clearly interpreted and have not received sufficient coverage. At the same time, there are quite a few works in modern scientific publications that study the possibility of random and/or systematic manipulation of information using AI algorithms.

Today, AI is built into many everyday technologies, such as smartphones and social networks. On the one hand, they are extremely necessary for people, but on the other hand, they are not taken seriously enough by them. Modern AI algorithms are even more invisible than the technologies they are built into. This allows for the constant receipt of user data, finding connections invisible to humans, creating user profiles and influencing their beliefs and consciousness. This results in bias in decision-making, and therefore direct manipulation of human behavior, which is substantiated in the works of M. Klenk [3] and S. Faraoni [4].

A team of authors J. Xu, D. Ju, M. Li, Y. Boureau, J. Weston, and E. Dinan [5] argue that AI algorithms like ChatGPT do not have beliefs, but they reflect opinions learned through training, and these opinions can be tweaked to produce the desired outcome. The researchers believe that the best defense against this new form of AI influence on humans is to make as many people as possible aware of it. In the long term, government regulation that ensures transparency about how AI algorithms work and what human biases they mimic will be helpful.

In recent years, Microsoft's research has paid much attention to such social issues as: the impact of AI algorithms on employment and job creation; responsibility in the use of AI; compliance with ethical principles for the protection of the population. Of decisive importance for reducing the negative social impact on society is compliance with the principles of security and safety of personal data, transparency and accountability in the development and practical application of AI algorithms [6]. Indeed, today AI algorithms have already become a significant part of the products and services that are used daily by the population.

Google's principles for using AI algorithms largely coincide with those of Microsoft. However, Google has already introduced a principle of refusing to participate in the development of AI algorithms if they are potentially capable of causing irreparable harm to the population of the entire planet [7].

In 2021, the UNESCO Recommendation on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence mentions manipulation of public opinion in connection with the use of cognitive biases for malicious purposes [8].

Based on the results of surveys of two groups (1,506 and 500 people), it was found that large AI language algorithms such as GPT-3 can form desired opinions and, thus, directly influence the consciousness of the general public [9]. Three areas of influence have been identified: behavioral norms; legal norms; information. However, the influence itself is difficult to determine, since the preferences for choosing opinions built into AI language algorithms are hidden from users. It should be taken into account that there is also a random influence on user beliefs through AI language algorithms. Therefore, the preferences formed by AI language algorithms will be different for different users, products, and content. Today, it is already an established opinion that interaction with AI language algorithms influences user opinions, even if this happens unintentionally. Obviously, we should be more careful in choosing opinions that developers build into AI language algorithms such as GPT-3.

An experimental study found that AI algorithms influence interpersonal perception, performance of management tasks, etc. [10]. The active and dynamic nature of AI algorithms can change the norms of communication between individuals. This suggests that AI language algorithms can distort interpersonal perception and contribute to the growth of social tension.

The issues of accounting for the accuracy of content when exchanging messages between social network users were studied in the work [3]. Usually, social network users distribute this or that content without thinking about its reliability. The distribution of knowingly false information opens up opportunities for manipulating the behavior and beliefs of various groups of individuals. A taxonomy of reasons by which people can determine that a message is true or false, and a checklist for determining the accuracy of information have been developed. According to the

results of a survey of 1668 participants, it was found that providing an assessment of the accuracy and justification of messages reduces the distribution of false content to a greater extent, the distribution of true content to a lesser extent. As a result, the share of distribution of false content decreases.

The influence of AI algorithms on the choice of preferences in various groups of society is studied both in academic structures and by their direct developers. At the same time, academic structures are significantly inferior in the volume of research conducted to AI developers [11]. This is why the most famous AI algorithms were developed in the interests of these companies. Hence, AI developers have the opportunity to explicitly or implicitly (intentionally or accidentally) manipulate the behavior of large groups of people.

Thus, the problem of AI manipulability exists. The existing results of studying this problem do not allow us to clearly determine the volumes and level of manipulation that are embedded in modern AI algorithms. According to the authors, in the language of mathematics it can be represented through a shift in estimates and a narrowing of the variability of user actions.

2. The influence of AI algorithms on the change of basic values of Russian society

From the theoretical side, these issues are covered in the works of: D.M. Semenova, M.V. Afonin and S.A. Kudryavtsev [12]; V.Yu. Litvinov and L.V. Matveeva [13]; V.I. Pantin [14]; S.D. Savin and M.S. Kasabutskaya [15]; A.D. Kharichev, A.Yu. Shutov, A.V. Polosin and E.N. Sokolov [16]; V.Sh. The authors of these theoretical works use many different non-formalized criteria for evaluation. For this reason, they are not suitable for testing AI algorithms. As is known, in order to increase the efficiency of any testing, it is necessary to determine the composition of key indicators. At the semantic level, they are enshrined in the “Fundamentals of State Policy for the Preservation and Strengthening of Traditional Russian Spiritual and Moral Values” (approved by Decree of the President of Russia No. 809 of November 9, 2022). However, these indicators cannot be measured quantitatively.

Formalized quantitative indicators for assessing civilizational values are presented in the work [17]. Five key indicators are identified: long-term orientation, certainty of the future, distance from power, individuality, masculinity. Based on G. Hofstede’s methodology, a comparative analysis of Russia’s values with those of the West (see Fig. 1 [17, p. 35]) and the East (see Fig. 2 [17, p. 36]) is performed.

Fig. 1. Comparison of civilizational values of Russia and Western countries.

Fig. 2. Comparison of civilizational values of Russia and the countries of the East.

The results of the analysis revealed the axiological type of Russia and the main value contradiction between individualism and collectivism.

The World Values Survey project studies quantitative criteria for choosing the value orientation of different groups among almost 100 countries of the world. The results of a large number of surveys served as the basis for this. Ronald Inglehart's system was used for the assessment. Civilization values were compared in two directions: tradition-secularity and collectivism-individualism. As a result, a clear

distribution of countries into clusters was obtained depending on the prevailing civilization values. Russia is assigned to the "Orthodox" cluster (highlighted in red) (see Fig. 3 [18]). In terms of its civilization values, it is significantly removed from the "Protestant" (marked in yellow) and "Anglo-Saxon" (marked in dark green) clusters. Thus, quantitative assessments confirm the existence of a global confrontation between Russia and Western countries, between which there is the greatest distance in terms of civilizational values.

Fig. 3. Remoteness of country clusters according to civilizational values.

Since the civilizational values of any country change over time, in addition to axiological assessments, their direction should be determined. In the long term, this will allow us to identify the convergence or divergence of various clusters according to civilizational values. The World Values Survey project made it possible to determine the main direction of the dynamics of civilizational values (see Fig. 4 [18]).

We did not find any other studies that would somehow systematize quantitative assessments of civilizational values. Since the “individualism-collectivism” factor is one of the key criteria for the Russian

civilizational model, the authors considered it legitimate to use it in this study.

When presenting the problem of the impact of AI on public consciousness through the bias of assessments and the narrowing of their variability, it is necessary to take into account the presence of random and/or systemic manipulation of AI algorithms. In the work of I.D. Grachev and N.V. Noak, the significance of the actually observed narrowing of the diversity of AI with symmetrical errors in assessing their activities for the economic growth of subjects was substantiated [19]. This is clearly confirmed by the graph (see Fig. 5 [20]).

Fig. 4. Dynamics of civilizational values (since 1981).

Fig. 5. Narrowing of the diversity of AI with symmetric errors in assessing the actions of subjects.

The nature of the influence of AI algorithms on factors that are obviously asymmetrical to estimation errors and agent actions is shown in Figure 6 [19].

The results obtained indicate that a differentiated approach based on the selection of key indicators is needed to study the influence of AI algorithms on public consciousness. With regard to living systems, the main indicator of their vital activity is the ratio of "chaos and order".

Since a community of people can also be considered a living system, the authors believe that the "individualism-collectivism" factor fully reflects this relationship in public consciousness. Moreover, as was established earlier, this factor is one of the basic differences of the Russian civilization model. On this basis, it will be included in the most significant factors in further research on the influence of AI algorithms on human behavior and changes in the basic values of Russian society.

Fig. 6. Narrowing of the diversity of AI with obviously asymmetric errors in assessing the actions of subjects.

Conclusion

All over the world, processes related to the emergence of new knowledge are actively taking place. Many of them are directly related to the introduction of AI into people's daily life. The intensification of discussions and the contradictory nature of attitudes only confirm the rapid development of AI algorithms. They can open up new opportunities and prospects for the development of AI in the interests of the global community, as well as pose today quite tangible threats to its existence in the near future.

In modern conditions, it is important to consider the risks of introducing AI algorithms into people's everyday life. The negative impact of narrowing variability for situations of various deviations, as well as deliberate errors made by content moderators

when posting information, allows us to conclude that it is advisable to use a differentiated approach to assessing the impact of AI algorithms on the consciousness of each person and society as a whole based on various factors.

The article substantiates the need to use a systemic approach to reduce the risk of negative impact of English-language AI algorithms on Russian civilizational values.

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